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OUR NATIONAL VALUES IN THE FORM OF A NATIONAL IDEAL

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Thanks to independence, the Uzbek people got the foundations of their traditional national statehood, formed over many millennia. From the first days of independence, all major countries of the world recognized Uzbekistan as a full member of the international community.

With the will of our people, we started to establish a legal democratic state and a free civil society based on the market economy. The achieved national independence made serious changes in the country's political system. Today's development of our society requires the formation of harmony of universal and national ideals.

The unique aspect of each nation is based on its moral values. The root of society's morality is a phenomenon inextricably linked with the history of the nation. From youth, a person grows up surrounded by age-old traditions and customs.

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If the freedom factor is used without purpose, it will have a negative impact on the development of social consciousness. "Freedom is not tyranny and anarchy. A person who deviates from the law, deviates from tradition and commits immorality is not a free person, but a destroyer and someone who encroaches on the freedom of others. Therefore, it is necessary to solve the problem of understanding and understanding that there is no absolute freedom in society, that independent thinking is not irresponsibility and forgetting one's duty.

Today, all peaceful humanity wants an enlightened world. In the enlightened world, there is a moral agreement between states, political forces, and opposition parties. Moral agreement is the level of interest in coordinating the goals of countries and peoples, regardless of the level of development, location, population, social orientation, views, culture, and religion, and the level of interest in harmonizing the goals of the common development.

Achieving this state is extremely difficult. At the current stage of social development, the changes taking place in the world, conflicts and disagreements between states and political forces undoubtedly do not allow such an agreement. This is a very sad situation. As we mentioned above, the high intellectual level of the world, the ever-increasing knowledge and skills of humanity, the development of new rules for solving problems in civilized ways, and the increasing number of new types of global problems are locking the countries and peoples of the world into a dead end.

Therefore, Independence is the basis for the national ideal. We see the buds of the national ideal in historical stages, but independence turned them into real social reality. It is not easy to change the ideal, it is mainly realized by heart, soul, mind and whole body. Only the idea that is ingrained in the heart, soul, and mind of the human body becomes an ideal. The national idea takes place in the hearts of our people as a social ideal, and it is connected with philosophical and spiritual processes and researches, such as turning into the life goal and hopes of every person. Achieving spiritual growth requires creative research and active action from the people and the nation for centuries.

People believe in the ideal. However, it is observed in many cases that going beyond the limit or not following the norm leads to negative consequences. In our opinion, at the turning points of its history, each nation first of all solves the issue of the national ideal, its history, which serves as a unique axis, a unifying nucleus, and the problem of forming a national idea. That is why it is emphasized that the national idea has an important place as a force that positively influences democratic processes and mobilizes people.

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